

ON THE ISSUE OF INCREASING MOTIVATION FOR LEARNING A FOREIGN LANGUAGES IN NON-LINGUISTIC UNIVERSITIES

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Annotation

The article is devoted to the issue of increasing the motivation of learning a foreign language in non-linguistic universities. The author considers the issues of improving the quality and successful performance of professional tasks by future specialists of customs authorities. The disclosure of creative potential, the right choice of didactic material for learning a foreign language will form and improve the mental activity of students and arouse interest in its study. As well as issues of self-development will lead to the stimulation and development of sustainable, cognitive interest of students of non-linguistic universities.

Keywords: professional education, foreign language, motivation, personality-oriented approach, individual approach, cognitive interest, self-improvement, analytical thinking.

Today, a mandatory component of continuing professional education of the university is teaching foreign languages. The course of teaching foreign languages in universities is of a communicative-oriented and professionally-oriented nature and leads to the formation of communicative professional competence. Due to the trends of globalization and internationalization, the functional significance of foreign languages is increasing, and the issues of communicative teaching of a foreign language are of particular importance.

The process of preparation for professional activity as a system is formed under the influence of many factors and can be considered at three levels: as a process, as a state, and as a result. It represents the development by a future specialist of professional knowledge and experience necessary for the subsequent successful performance of professional tasks. Professional training of students of the Customs Institute – future officers with good knowledge of a foreign language – includes mastering the basics of general and special knowledge and applying them in practice, mastering skills and abilities for the successful performance of professional tasks of a cognitive, practical nature that will be used in future professional activities, the

formation of professional qualities important for a future customs officer with a foreign language.

The unification of efforts of customs authorities of different countries in the fight against drug smuggling and illegal distribution, the exchange of scientific and technical information and experience in the prevention of customs violations, the adoption of new international conventions, the harmonization of customs procedures and many other aspects of international customs cooperation emphasize the importance of knowledge of foreign languages and cultures that contribute to the resolution of difficulties in foreign economic activity arising from language barriers.

Many studies show that currently students of non-linguistic specialties have low motivation to study a foreign language, because a foreign language is a difficult subject that requires a lot of effort, time and perseverance. The conviction that it is impossible to overcome these obstacles, lack of self-confidence, and sometimes unwillingness to overcome certain difficulties, leads to a decrease in interest in a foreign language. Therefore, the main task facing the teacher is to reveal the creative potential of students, to find such didactic means that would awaken the mental activity of students and interest in a foreign language. It is important to create such conditions in the classroom in which students will have an interest and desire to learn a foreign language. Very often, the main goal when teaching a foreign language for many students is not to extract knowledge for their development and self-improvement, but to get an assessment. Therefore, it is necessary to stimulate the development of cognitive interest among students. They should realize why they need a foreign language, what its practical significance is for their future.

Currently, there is an active search for new methods in teaching foreign languages that can stimulate sustained cognitive interest in the learning process. In teaching foreign languages, there are different approaches, different strategies in teaching. The recognition of the personality-oriented approach as a new paradigm of education and upbringing has led to changes in the setting of goals, in the selection of content, principles and technologies of teaching foreign languages. The most important thing is to find a differentiated approach to the student, to take into account his capabilities, inclinations, needs. With regard to the content of teaching foreign languages, a problematic presentation of the material is necessary, showing the peculiarities of morals, customs and culture of people in our country and in

the countries of the studied language in comparison. One of the important points is that the emphasis is not on communicating ready-made knowledge, but on encouraging students to reflect, to independently search for information, to make independent conclusions and generalizations, as well as appeal to the life and speech experience of the students themselves. The student and the teacher in the learning process are always put in a situation of choice (texts, exercises, sequence of work). It should also be noted that the personality-oriented approach assumes that, showing independence in choosing one or another additional material, students proceed from their needs, interests, and this gives personal meaning to learning. This approach also provides for the development of their reflection, the ability to see themselves "from the outside", independently assess their capabilities and needs. The personality-oriented approach makes it possible to introduce active forms of learning into the educational process that contribute to the development of students' creative abilities, thinking, and the ability to rebuild in a rapidly changing modern society. The emphasis is on group and pair work, which "displace" the frontal forms of work. The most appropriate learning technologies are collaborative learning, the project method, and the inclusion of such types of work that cause emotional discharge of students. Choosing a method of teaching, the teacher should be aware that the main thing in studying the discipline is the formation of knowledge, skills, as well as the education and development of students.

Each of the methods used in pedagogical practice has its advantages and disadvantages, but using them in the system, in conjunction, will help to achieve the best results in the assimilation of knowledge by students and in the development of their mental activity. The choice of methods depends on a number of conditions: on the specifics of the content of the material being studied, on the general tasks of training specialists, on the teaching time available to the teacher, the characteristics of the composition of students, on the availability of teaching tools.

Social networks, as well as funny videos can also increase interest in the subject and develop the cognitive skills of the cadet. The same videos directly related to the topic of the specialty can be developed and filmed by the cadets themselves in the form of independent work proposed by the teacher. Cadets can take part in Internet contests, Olympiads, create multimedia presentations while working on thematic projects, carry out

various work with texts in the specialty to prepare their own reports, presentations and answers in the audience.

A positive result for the formation of analytical skills of students is directly dependent on the means and conditions in which this quality will be formed.

The following conditions can be distinguished:

- 1) individual approach to the student;
- 2) creating comfortable (psychological) conditions in which the creative potential of students will be revealed;
- 3) careful selection of educational material that is meaningful and interesting for students (the use of authentic materials, as well as a huge number of educational resources in text, audio and video formats);
- 4) application of new technologies in teaching foreign languages (group, pair work, individual).

As many researchers note, analytical skills are formed in various cognitive and research exercises, situational and game exercises, problem situations, various competitions, role-playing games. All this contributes to the activation of students' mental activity, namely the ability to compare, compare, draw conclusions, that is, the activation of analytical operations.

Thus, it can be argued that active methods are aimed at creating a favorable motivational and emotional background in the classroom of a foreign language, which leads to the development of a sustained interest in its mastery and forms the analytical thinking of students, activates mental activity, reveals their creative abilities.

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